

**SUPERSTITIOUS ATTITUDE IN RELATION TO ADJUSTMENT OF PROSPECTIVE
TEACHERS**

Shivani Pathania* & Dr. Anurag Sankhian**

ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to study the superstitious attitude and adjustment of the prospective teachers. This research study also examined the relationship between superstitious attitude and adjustment of prospective teachers. The sample comprised of 100 prospective teachers including 50 male and 50 female prospective teachers from the district Kangra of Himachal Pradesh. The tools used for conducting the present study were, Superstitious attitude scale developed by Dr Shailja Bhagwat (2006) and Adjustment inventory for college students developed by A.K.P. Sinha and R.P. Singh (2005). The results of this research study show that there exists no significant difference between the superstitious attitude of male and female prospective teachers. Study also found that there exist no significant correlation between the superstitious attitude and adjustment of prospective teachers.

INTRODUCTION

Education plays an important role in removing the darkness from the life of the masses and in improving the quality of their life. Attitude contributes a lot in teaching and it can be defined in many ways. Attitude means the individuals prevailing tendency to respond favorably or unfavorably to an object, persons, different people in a group, or in institutions and different events etc. Hogg and Vaughan (2005) stated that, “An attitude is a relative the enduring organization of beliefs, feeling and behavioral tendencies to what socially significant objects, groups, events or symbols”. Superstition is defined as a collection of unreasonable belief about the cause and effect that is the conviction that the future is affected by certain actions without any logical, casual relationship. Society shape the attitude of a person and most of the superstitious beliefs are developed through the process of socialization of an individual.

***M.Ed. Student, Government College of Education, Sector-20 D, Chandigarh**

**** Associate Professor, Government college of Education, Sector-20 D, Chandigarh**

Though, such beliefs can be divided into some categories like cultural, religious and personal. Foster, Weigand & Baines(2006) stated that, “*Superstition is a behavior which does not have a clear technical function in the execution of skill, yet which is believed to control luck and other external factors*”. Adjustment in simple words can be defined as satisfactory relations of person to his environment. It is a state that is the condition of harmony arrived at by a person whom we call ‘well adjusted’. Well adjusted person always feel satisfied from the life. According to Shaffer (1961),“*Adjustment is the process by which living organism maintains a balance between its needs and circumstances that inference the satisfaction of these needs*”.

Rudoff (1984) conducted a study on a sample of the 100 professors & 100 students to observe the religious and social behavior among academics & concluded that there is congruence between social value and religious norms. Gupta (1999) revealed in his study that law students were more prone to superstitious beliefs than the medical and engineering students. Rudski (2001) placed undergraduate students in a competitive environment to measure superstition and illusion of control & found a link supporting self-efficacy and increased use of superstition. Sagone & Elvira (2014) in their study ‘*Locus of control & beliefs about superstition and luck in adolescents*’ mentioned that, there may be a strong link between the holding of superstitious beliefs and the need to cope with the un-controlling of life also, during the adolescent. Kose (2015) in his study entitled, ‘*The dimensions of superstitious beliefs & behavior*’ revealed five factors of superstitious belief and named such as lucky behaviors, to teams, bad luck belief, lucky items and ignore. Ter Keurst (2015) investigated about the extent of the home a source of beliefs and disbelief in superstitions. Tamilselvi & Sindhu (2016) revealed in his study that superstitions don’t differ significantly between the groups’ classified in terms of gender, religion & subject of specialization. Olorundare (2019) in his research study identified the nature, prevalence & effect of superstitious beliefs and analysed the types & degrees of superstitious beliefs.

Coleman (1960) contented in his study entitled ‘*Personality dynamics & effective behavior*’ that good adjustment is not a state in which we feel no pain and no desire, it is a continuous successful meeting of inner and outer requirements, which change from person to person & year to year. Saini (1998) in his study found that the relationship of self esteem with total adjustment

was positive and significant for male, female & total sample. Armin (2010) conducted a study to examine the influence of gender on adjustment among adolescents & found that the gender had no differential influence over adjustment scores in home, health, emotional & social areas. Sharma (2013) in his research found that social intelligence and adjustment level of male was slightly more than the female pupil teachers in the college of education. Kumar (2015) conducted a research study to investigate the levels of attitudes towards teaching profession in relation to adjustment of senior secondary school teachers. Janardhanan & Murthy (2020) revealed in their study conducted among college students that gender, nature of course & age has significant differences on adjustment among college students. Superstitious attitude is not considered as a positive sign for the development of the society and teachers should always try to teach students to think rationally and scientifically while taking their day to day decisions. The present study was conducted with an objective to research the relation between superstitious attitude & adjustment level of the prospective teachers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study was conducted to attain the following objectives:

1. To study the superstitious attitude of the pupil teachers.
2. To study the adjustment level of the pupil teachers.
3. To compare the superstitious attitude of the male and female pupil teachers.
4. To compare the adjustment levels of the male and female pupil teachers.
5. To study the correlation between superstitious attitude and adjustment level of the pupil teachers.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The present study was conducted to test the following hypotheses:

1. There exists no significant difference in the superstitious attitude of the male and female pupil teachers.
2. There exists no significant difference in the adjustment level of the male and female pupil teachers.

3. There exists no significant correlation between the superstitious attitude and adjustment of the pupil teachers.

DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The study was delimited to 100 prospective teachers & the sample was selected randomly from the Teacher Education Colleges running B.Ed. course and located in the Kangra district of Himachal Pradesh only.

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

Method of Study

Descriptive survey method was used in the present study. This study covered two variables including superstitious attitude & adjustment

Sample of the Study

The study was conducted on a sample of 100 prospective teachers selected randomly. The prospective teachers were selected from Kangra district of Himachal Pradesh, in which 50 were male and 50 were female prospective teachers.

Tools used in the Study

The following tools were used for conducting this study:

1. Superstitious attitude scale (SAS) by Dr. Shailja Bhagwat (2006).
2. Adjustment inventory for college students (AICS) by Prof. A.K.P. Sinha & Prof. R.P. Singh (2005).

Statistical Techniques Used

Data was analyzed by calculating Mean, Median, Standard deviation, Skewness, and Kurtosis. t-test was applied to determine the significance of the differences between the means. Pearson's product moment correlation was used to compute and to determine the relationship between superstitious attitude and adjustment level of the pupil teachers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

H01: There exists no significant difference in superstitious attitude of the male and female pupil teachers

TABLE 1: DIFFERENCE BETWEEN SUPERSTITIOUS ATTITUDE OF MALE AND FEMALE PUPIL TEACHERS

Pupil Teacher	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Degree of Freedom	t-value	Level of significance
Male	50	58.96	11.56	98	0.56	<i>Non-Significant</i>
Female	50	57.66	11.49			

Table 1 shows that the mean scores for the superstitious attitude for male and female prospective teachers are 58.96 & 57.66 respectively with standard deviation 11.56 and 11.49. The mean scores for the superstitious attitude for male (58.96) were found higher in comparison to the female (57.66) pupil teachers. There exists a non-significant difference between superstitious attitude of male and female pupil teachers as t-ratio (t-value=0.56) was found in significant. Hence, Hypothesis H01: “*There exists no significant difference in the superstitious attitude of the male and female pupil teachers*” is accepted.

H02: There exists no significant difference in the adjustment level of the male and female pupil teachers

TABLE 2: DIFFERENCE BETWEEN ADJUSTMENT LEVEL OF THE MALE AND FEMALE PUPIL TEACHERS

Prospective Teacher	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Degree of Freedom	t-value	Level of significance
Male	50	48.14	16.74	98	0.86	<i>Non-Significant</i>
Female	50	45.34	15.42			

Table 2 shows the mean scores for the adjustment level for male and female pupil teachers as 48.14 & 45.34 respectively with standard deviation 16.74 and 15.42. There exists a non-significant difference between adjustment level of male and female pupil teachers as t-ratio (t-value=0.86) was found insignificant. Hence hypothesis H02: '*There exists no significant difference in adjustment level of male and female pupil teachers*' is accepted.

H03: There exists no significant correlation between the superstitious attitude & adjustment of the pupil teachers

TABLE 3: COEFFICIENT OF CORRELATION BETWEEN SUPERSTITIOUS ATTITUDE AND ADJUSTMENT LEVEL OF THE PUPIL TEACHERS

Variable	N	r -value
Superstitious attitude & Adjustment	100	0.12

Table 3 reveals that Pearson correlation coefficient value between superstitious attitude and adjustment of the pupil teachers which was found to be 0.12 which is not significant. Hence the H03: '*There exists no significant correlation between the superstitious attitude and adjustment of pupil teachers*' is accepted.

CONCLUSION

1. There exists no significant difference in the superstitious attitude of male and female prospective teachers.
2. There exists no significant difference in the adjustment level of male and female prospective teachers.
3. There exists no significant correlation between superstitious attitude and adjustment level of prospective teachers.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

Careful steps should be adopted to develop positive attitude towards adjustment among prospective teachers and essentially it will bring development in the society. Such studies will also be useful in educating the society about the side effects of superstitious attitude. The result of the present study and if more such studies are conducted in future, this will help in assessing the superstitious attitude and adjustment level of the prospective teachers who will be having the responsibility of shaping the personality and guiding the children. This study will also help to develop scientific approach among prospective teachers which will help them to make necessary improvements in themselves. The present study was conducted on a small sample of 100 prospective teachers selected randomly from the Kangra district of Himachal Pradesh. It is recommended that more such type of the studies should be conducted for getting clearer picture about the selected variables.

REFERENCES

- Armin. M. (2010). Influences Gender on Adjustment among Adolescents. *Asian Journal of Development Matters*, 4(1), 216-219.
- Bhagawat, S. (2006). *Manual for Superstitious Attitude Scale*, H.P. Bhargava Book House Kacherighat, Agra, India.
- Coleman, E. (1960). *Personality Dynamics & Effective Behavior*. Illinois; Scott Foresman and Company Glenview.
- Foster, D. J., Weigand, D. A., and Baines, D. (2006). The Effect of Removing Superstitious Behaviour. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, 18(2), 167-171.
- Gupta, N. K., (1999). A research on superstitious behavior amongst the professional graduates and law students. Retrieved from <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in>.
- Hogg, M., & Vaughan, G. (2005). *Social Psychology*, (4th edition). London: Prentice-Hall .
- Janardhanam, V. & Murthy, P.V. (2020). Adjustment among college students, *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*, 11(2), 37464-37465. RDOI: 10.24327/IJRSR

- Kose, Huseyin. et al., (2015). The Dimensions of Superstitious Beliefs and Behaviors: A Descriptive Quantitative Study on Soccer Fans in Turkey. *International Journal of Global Business*. Vol – 8, Issue- 1, pp-27-33.
- Kumar, A. (2015). Attitude towards Teaching Profession in Relation to Adjustment among Senior Secondary School Teachers. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 4(4), 830-833. Retrieved from https://www.ijsr.net/search_index_results_paperid.php?id=SUB153131
- Olorundare, S., (2019). Superstitious beliefs as constraints in the learning of science, *Nigerian Journal of Guidance and Counselling*, 6(1), DOI: 10.4314/njgc.v6i1.37083
- Rudski (2001). Competition, Superstition and illusion of control. *Current Psychology*. 20, pp 68–84
- Rudoff , H (1984) . A study to observe religious and social behavior among academics in both professors and students. Retrieved from shodhanga.inflibnet.ac.in
- Saini, A. (1998). A study of self esteem in relation to gender, discipline of teaching, anxiety and adjustment. (In H B Buch: A Survey of Research in Education, published by Centre of Advance Study of Education, 1998.)
- Sagone, E., & Elvira, D. C., (2014). Locus Of Control and Beliefs About Superstition and Luck in Adolescents: What's Their Relationship? *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. Science Direct, pp-318-323. Retrieved from http://ac.els-cdn.com/S1877042814033539/1-s2.0-S1877042814033539-main.pdf?_tid=788d31c8-87b711e7bcd100000aab0f26&acdnat=1503460953_94ea53241916b2c7342588c6a1eee9f6
- Shaffer (1961). Adjustments status of students in relation to intelligence. *Foundation of Psychology*, New York, p.511
- Shakuntala, K.S. and Subapathy, T.(1999). Teacher Adjustment is related to interest in attitude towards Teaching. *Journal of Psychology*, Vol. 16, No. 3.

Sharma, S. (2013). Social intelligence of students' teachers in colleges of education in relation to adjustment. *Recent researches in Education and Psychology*, Volume 18

Sinha, A. K. P. & Singh, R. P. (2005). Adjustment Inventory for college students, National Psychological Corporation, Bhargava Bhawan, 4/230, Kacheri Ghat, Agra.

Tamilselvi, B., Sindhu, B. (2016). A study of superstitions among higher secondary school teachers in Kerala, *International Education and Research Journal*. 2(11), 45-47.

TerKerust, A. J. (2015). The Acceptance of Superstitious Beliefs among Secondary School. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 32(9), 673-685.